

Considerations in the Anesthetic Management of the Patient With Nasal Inverted Papilloma: Clinical Case Report

Alexia Palma Meza¹, Roberto Isaac Vázquez Espinola²

¹Third-year Anesthesiology Resident. Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán.

²Anesthesiologist, assigned to the Anesthesiology service-Assistant Professor of the Anesthesiology service. Hospital Regional de Alta Especialidad de la Península de Yucatán.

ABSTRACT

The present clinical case report describes the anesthetic management of an adult patient with Nasal Inverted Papilloma undergoing functional endoscopic paranasal sinus surgery and tumor resection in a third-level hospital. Sinonasal inverted papilloma is a benign tumor with a tendency for recurrence and a risk of malignant transformation. The usual treatment is surgical excision. These types of cases present intraoperative challenges such as airway control classified as difficult, difficult ventilation, and hemodynamic stability. Therefore, nasal tumor embolization was chosen with the objective of reducing bleeding and facilitating excision.

KEYWORDS: Nasal Tumor Embolization, Anesthetic Management, Otolaryngology, Nasal Inverted Papilloma, Difficult Airway.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
21 April 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Nasal inverted papilloma is a benign epithelial neoplasm of the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses characterized by endophytic growth of the respiratory epithelium into the underlying stroma. This confers a potentially aggressive clinical behavior with a high probability of local recurrence if not completely resected (Stawski, 2017). "It owes its name to the appearance of the inverted epithelium in the stroma, with a clear and intact basement membrane, which separates the epithelial component from the underlying connective tissue stroma" (Armenta et al, 2024, p.140).

This tumor represents between 0.5% and 4% of all nasal neoplasms and most frequently occurs in middle-aged adults, especially in males (Stawski, 2017; Jiang et al, 2017). Armenta et al (2024) state that its incidence varies between 0.2 and 1.5 cases per 100,000 inhabitants per year and that it is a tumor that occurs mostly in male patients; "with a frequency of between 2 and 5 men for every woman and the majority of patients are between 55 and 59 years old" (Armenta et al, 2024, p.140).

Within the variety presented by the histological type of nasal papillomas, 3 can be differentiated: 1) Everted or exophytic papillomas, 2) Cylindrical cell papillomas or oncocyctic papilloma, 3) Inverted papillomas or Schneiderian papilloma (Llorente, 2007).

In the case of everted or exophytic papillomas, these are well-differentiated papillomas with hyperkeratosis that develop almost exclusively in the vestibular area, septum and even in the head of the inferior turbinate and usually present as a single and unilateral lesion, except in the nasal vestibule, which can be diffuse. They can recur, but their malignant potential is very doubtful. There is growing evidence that their etiology is related to the human papillomavirus (HPV). The treatment is complete surgical excision (Llorente, 2007). The cylindrical cell papilloma or oncocyctic papilloma represents 5-10% of all papillomas. They can become malignant in a percentage slightly higher than the inverted papilloma (17%). It usually develops on the lateral nasal wall, with a propensity to grow in the maxillary antrum without affecting the nasal fossa. This group has not been related to HPV. Its treatment is surgical and its prognosis similar to that of the inverted papilloma (Llorente, 2007).

The inverted papilloma or Schneiderian papilloma is the most frequent and representative and usually grows on the lateral wall of the nasal passages including the ethmoid and maxillary sinus. It is not actually a papilloma, but rather a polypoid change of the nasal mucosa accompanied by severe metaplasia within the polypous tissue, both of the respiratory epithelium and the glandular ducts, which can even be difficult to distinguish from a low-grade squamous

Considerations in the Anesthetic Management of the Patient With Nasal Inverted Papilloma: Clinical Case Report

carcinoma. It should be emphasized that there are no intermediate forms between these three types of lesions (Llorente, 2007).

The etiology of nasal inverted papilloma is multifactorial and not yet completely understood. There is evidence suggesting a possible association with human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, being reported in a significant percentage of cases and especially implicated in lesions with a risk of malignant transformation (ErgueraAguirre et al., 2022; Llorente, 2007). Said association remains a matter of controversy due to variability in HPV detection in different clinical series (Llorente, 2007). Additionally, environmental factors such as smoking have been linked to a greater tendency for post-surgical recurrence, probably due to chronic inflammation of the mucosa that favors the persistence of the lesion (Stawski, 2017).

Clinically, inverted papilloma can manifest as unilateral nasal obstruction, recurrent epistaxis, and persistent rhinorrhea (Mena et al., 2010; Waissbluth et al., 2018). The diagnosis of nasal inverted papilloma is multimodal and integrates clinical evaluation, imaging studies, and histopathological confirmation.

Clinical evaluation: symptoms are generally insidious and unilateral, with persistent nasal obstruction, epistaxis and, in some cases, headache and purulent rhinorrhea, which can initially lead to erroneous diagnoses such as chronic sinusitis (Waissbluth et al, 2018).

Imaging: computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are indispensable for studying tumor extension, defining the relationship with bony structures and paranasal sinuses, and planning the surgical approach. CT helps evaluate bony involvement, while MRI is useful for differentiating the tumor from surrounding inflammatory tissue (Salazar et al, 2011).

Histopathology: definitive diagnostic confirmation is made by biopsy with an anatomopathological study, which shows the characteristic epithelial proliferation of inverted papilloma ; furthermore, it is crucial for ruling out associated malignant transformation, especially to squamous carcinoma in areas of atypia (ErgueraAguirre et al., 2022).

Regarding the surgical approach, it should be mentioned that surgical techniques have evolved from open approaches to endoscopic surgery; however, the type of approach will depend on the tumor location (Armenta et al, 2024). On their part, authors such as Jiang et al (2017) state that the treatment of choice for nasal inverted papilloma is surgical, with the objective of removing the tumor with free margins to minimize recurrence. In this sense, functional endoscopic nasal surgery (FESS) has demonstrated high efficacy and lower rates of persistence and recurrence when performed properly, which makes it the preferred method in most cases, provided the tumor extension allows it (Martínez, et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2017).

Similarly, techniques with combined and open approaches exist, given that in tumors with complex extensions, invasion

of sinuses or adjacent structures, a combined approach (endoscopic + open) or classical techniques such as lateral rhinotomy, Caldwell-Luc or craniofacial may be required to achieve complete resection and margin control (Ordoñez & Carballo, 2018; Llorente et al., 2013). The selected approach must consider tumor extension and the experience of the surgical team, with prolonged postoperative follow-up to detect late recurrences.

ANESTHETIC CONSIDERATIONS

Anesthesia in nasal inverted papilloma surgery involves specific strategies due to the vascular nature of the surgical field and the need for optimal conditions for the surgeon. In this scenario, general anesthesia is the preferred technique in most rhinosinusal procedures as it allows complete control of the airway, facilitating prolonged manipulation and the possibility of complex surgical techniques such as FESS or combined approaches (Avila et al, 2024).

Bleeding control is a basic practice during nasal surgery due to the high vascularity of the mucosa. Anesthetic strategies such as controlled hypotension reduce the risk of intense hemorrhage and improve endoscopic visibility, allowing for greater surgical precision (Avila et al, 2024). Additionally, the use of local vasoconstrictors (such as adrenaline in solution) contributes to minimizing intraoperative bleeding.

Induced Hypotension: Maintaining a mean arterial pressure (MAP) between 60-70 mmHg is the gold standard for reducing mucosal bleeding.

Bradycardia: A low heart rate is usually more effective than hypotension itself.

Anesthetic Technique

TIVA (Total Intravenous Anesthesia): The use of Propofol and Remifentanyl is preferable over inhaled gases. Halogenated agents are potent vasodilators that can increase blood flow in the nasal mucosa, worsening bleeding.

Local Infiltration: The use of local epinephrine by the surgeon helps, but watch out for sudden arrhythmias or hypertensive spikes.

Exhaustive hemodynamic monitoring (ECG, invasive or non-invasive blood pressure, pulse oximetry, and capnography) is essential given the possibility of sudden changes during the procedure, especially in patients with cardiovascular or hematological comorbidities that may increase the risk of complications (Avila et al, 2016; Stawski, 2017). Preoperative planning must also include airway assessment and preparation for managing possible difficulties.

CLINICAL CASE DESCRIPTION

A 55-year-old male patient originally from and residing in Mérida, Yucatán. Weight:

104 kg. Height: 1.70 mt. BMI: [Value not listed]. Blood type: O(+).

The illness began 17 years ago with the presence of polyps at the level of the nasal passages, causing obstruction. Since his first surgical intervention, the size has gradually increased

Considerations in the Anesthetic Management of the Patient With Nasal Inverted Papilloma: Clinical Case Report

until presenting complete obstruction of the nasal passages, presenting constant hyaline and serohematic secretion, exophthalmos, headache, and diplopia. During the physical examination, the patient is observed to be of an age consistent with the chronological age, neurologically intact, eyes symmetrical with exophthalmos, pupils isocoric, punctate, nostrils with tumor in both nasal passages that limit air flow, oral cavity hydrated, own teeth, fixed.

During the exploration of the airway, Mallampati Class III, Sternomental distance Class II, Patil Aldreti Class II, Mandibular Protrusion Class II, short, thick cylindrical neck are observed. Thorax normolinear, lung fields with adequate air entry and exit, precordium normodynamic, rhythmic heart sounds, no audible murmurs, globose abdomen at the expense of adipose panniculus, limbs intact, symmetrical, without edema.

Chronic-degenerative history denied, previous anesthetic-surgical history positive on 6 occasions, allergies denied, transfusions positive without adverse reactions, drug addictions denied.

Diagnosis: Nasal inverted papilloma. **Treatment:** functional endoscopic paranasal sinus surgery + resection.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

12-lead electrocardiogram: standard calibration, sinus rhythm, axis slightly deviated to the right, HR 82bpm, PR 160msec, QRS 93msec, Q wave in DIII, without other alteration.

Chest X-ray: without evidence of apparent pleuropulmonary alteration.

Simple brain magnetic resonance imaging: neoplasm of both nasal passages involves superior, middle and inferior turbinates, invades ethmoid sinuses, with extension to the nasopharynx, introduction of the arachnoid into the sella turca.

Cranial panangiography: through digital subtraction angiography acquisitions, with injection of non-ionic contrast medium through both external carotid arteries, tumor staining dependent on the internal maxillary arteries is observed, predominantly the left. However, on the right side, the orbital component presents scant staining through the ipsilateral orbital branch; it has approximate dimensions of up to 72×37×53mm in the largest component (nasal) in its major axes.

Laboratory: Hemoglobin 15.4, Hematocrit 44%, Leukocytes 11.46, Platelets 325,000, PT 12.6 sec, APTT 32.5 sec, INR 0.81, Glucose 130mg/dL, Creatinine 1.16, Urea 30, Uric acid 8.3, triglycerides 126, HDL 36.4, LDL 174, Sodium 139 mmol/L, Potassium 3.9 mmol/L, Chloride 101 mmol/L.

SURGICAL TECHNIQUE AND ANESTHETIC MANAGEMENT

Anesthetic plan: Balanced general anesthesia, advanced airway management through video laryngoscopy blade 3 + Invasive monitoring through the right radial artery.

Induction is performed with Fentanyl (5mcg/kg), Lidocaine (1 mg/kg), Propofol (1.5mg/kg), Rocuronium (0.6mg/kg). Assisted ventilation is started, presenting problems in ventilation with HAN III scale. When performing video laryngoscopy, POGO 100% is observed without complications. Maintenance with lidocaine infusion at 20mcg/kg/min, Fentanyl 39mcg/kg/min, dexmedetomidine 0.50.7 mcg/kg/hr. As well as transanesthetic requirement of norepinephrine in infusion at dose-response to maintain Mean Arterial Pressure of 65mmHg with a maximum dose of 0.2mcg/kg/min. The anesthetic-surgical event ends with bleeding of 800ml.

Post-anesthetic plan: Patient enters the ICU for surveillance and continuous monitoring.

NASAL TUMOR EMBOLIZATION

Nasal tumor embolization was chosen, since this procedure allows blocking blood flow to tumors in the nasal cavity or paranasal sinuses. This procedure is used mainly in highly vascularized tumors with the objective of reducing bleeding, facilitating excision, and increasing the safety of the operation (Jiang, Dong, Li, Huang, & Zhang, 2017). Through a 7fr femoral introducer, a 5fr diagnostic catheter is navigated with a hydrophilic guide, and bilateral nasal tumor embolization was performed with polyvinyl-alcohol microparticles.

CONCLUSION

Nasal inverted papilloma is a benign but clinically challenging entity, with a high tendency for recurrence and risk of malignant transformation. Diagnosis requires a combination of clinical study, advanced imaging, and histopathological confirmation. The treatment of choice is surgical, with functional endoscopic nasal surgery predominating due to its better results and lower morbidity. Anesthetic considerations for these procedures must optimize hemodynamic and bleeding control to facilitate an adequate surgical field and ensure patient safety.

In the described case, the selected approach was functional endoscopic paranasal sinus surgery and tumor resection; which, as various authors point out (Martínez, et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2017), has demonstrated high efficacy and lower rates of persistence and recurrence, making it an adequate method for most cases, as long as the tumor extension allows it. Nasal tumor embolization was chosen with the objective of reducing bleeding and facilitating excision. A 7fr femoral introducer was used, navigated with a 5fr diagnostic catheter, with a hydrophilic guide; bilateral nasal tumor was embolized with polyvinyl-alcohol microparticles.

REFERENCES

1. Armenta, R., Bravo, M., & Guzmán, A. (2024). Papiloma nasal invertido: aspectos epidemiológicos en una muestra de pacientes mexicanos. *An Orl Mex*, 139-145.

Considerations in the Anesthetic Management of the Patient With Nasal Inverted Papilloma: Clinical Case Report

- II. Avila, J. L., Pilco, J. A., D. W., Gallardo, A. A., Zambrano, D. L., Romero, S. B., & Rodríguez, C. V. (2024). Estrategias Anestésicas para Intervenciones en Cavidad Nasal. *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, 20682079.
- III. Erguera-Aguirre, L. R., C.-C. A., & Pichardo-Bahena, R. (2022). Carcinoma epidermoide en el contexto de papiloma nasal invertido. *Anales de Otorrinolaringología mexicana*, 151-155.
- IV. Jiang, X., Dong, Q., Li, S., Huang, T., & Zhang, N. (2017). Endoscopic surgery of a sinonasal inverted papilloma: Surgical strategy, follow-up, and recurrence rate. *Rhinol Allergy*, 51-55.
- V. Llorente, J. (2007). Papilomas invertidos nasosinusales. *CIRUGÍA*
 - a. *ENDOSCÓPICA AVANZADA DE BASE DE CRÁNEO Y ESPACIOS PARANASALES*, 78-83.
- VI. Martínez, M. d., Bosco, G., Amarillo, E., Navarro, A., Jaquero, M. I., RodríguezUribe, T., & Plaza, G. (2022). Eficacia del tratamiento quirúrgico del papiloma invertido nasosinusal. *Revista ORL*.
- VII. Ordoñez, L., & Carballo, J. (2018). Papiloma invertido, presentación de un caso y revisión de la literatura. *Acta de Otorrinolaringología & Cirugía de Cabeza y Cuello*, 15-21.
- VIII. Salazar, J. X., Paredes, J. R., & J., M. (2011). Papilomas invertidos nasosinusales. *Revista Española de Cirugía Oral y Maxilofacial*, 138-141.
- IX. Stawski, R. (2017). Revisión de papiloma invertido. *OSECAC*, 1-6.
- X. Waissbluth, S., García, K., & Imarai, C. (2018). Cirugía endoscópica nasal en el tratamiento de papiloma invertido: A propósito de 18 casos. *Revista de otorrinolaringología y cirugía de cabeza y cuello*, 127-132.